

8T – High Energy Paradox

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the Primordial coupling constants series, author will argue that in order to detect those particles which are associated with higher coupling terms, i.e. weaker interactions, there exist a need for high energy collisions. That is to create bigger variational clusters, the bigger the cluster the higher the chance to detect those weaker Bosons.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of separation of the forces, i.e. Bosonic net variations. We have previously mentioned that the direction of the arrow is the direction of time. The strongest interactions appear at the first, the result is an endless process of clustering, with weaker and weaker interactions, given by ratio of net to total.

$$\begin{array}{c} \xrightarrow{\hspace{10em}} \\ 1 > \frac{3}{30} > \frac{5}{128} > \frac{7}{850} \dots \end{array}$$

When the author derived the coupling series back in March 2021, each coupling term was analyzed by extracting the net variation element. In the following page, presented the original part of the construction of the pre-equation idea which yielded the primorial:

Analyze the (7,11) total variations pair with $N_V = (+1)$:

Total variations sum is divisible by two:

$$18/2 = 9$$

And then by three

$$9/3 = 3$$

We know that we have $N_V = (+1)$ so it can be extracted to yield:

$$F_1 = 8 + 1$$

However, even amounts of variations vanish so we can ignore the element 8 and write:

$$F_1 = 1$$

Notice that the first interaction can be represented the following way:

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] = 9 \tag{1.62}$$

That is because each Boson is isomorphic to a prime, that was speculated on theorem two, pre-equation idea:

$$W^- \equiv +3$$

$$\gamma \equiv +5$$

so already in the first term we can represent the Bosons of the rest of the two interactions. Since we have taken it out from the total sum, we have separated it from the mixture of the three interactions. The Boson of the weak interaction can be either one of the three. We have taken W^- as it has the same charge as the electron, fact that the author used for the SUSY construction. So now after the Gluon was taken out:

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] \rightarrow [W^- + \gamma] + g$$

Next, the term in the parenthesis represents the Electroweak Bosonic combinations. This term create total sum of an even, and thus we took it to zero in the 8T thesis. However here we have two independent Bosons, so each can be set in his way. After the Gluon was separated, the electroweak combination is needed to be separated, to the electric Boson, the photon and the weak interaction Bosons. The combination of all the three also implies higher state of energy and as each interaction stands on its own, the energy is lower. So already we can reason why the forces should be separated.

$$[W^- + \gamma + g] \rightarrow E_n + E_{n+1} + E_{n+2} = E_{3n+3}$$

$$E_{3n+3} > E_n \cap E_{n+1} \cap E_{n+2}$$

That is to state that the SEW combined term has a higher energy state and each of the Bosons in itself, which indicate nature aspires to "break the combination" of the SEW into separated elements. It is quite a remarkable fact that the Bosons of the first three interactions sum exactly to the term of the first interaction to equation (1.62). Therefore, the 8T predicts that first the strong is separated than the Electroweak combined term. Now we are left with the question of detection of those higher coupling terms that are getting weaker as the arrow develops. Reason might indicate that to detect in order to detect those weaker interactions, civilization ought to examine weaker and weaker energies. Author will argue that the opposite is the case. To detect those weaker interactions we need higher energies. That is the case, as there exist a clear pattern given by the primorial. The clusters of variations, excluding the invariant three and the N_V element are getting larger from term to term:

$$2N_1 < 2N_2 < 2N_3$$

Put more elegantly

$$2N_k \rightarrow \infty$$

$$K \in \mathbb{R}$$

are the cluster of total variations which vanish into matter. That means that the increase the chance $2N_k$ of detecting the weaker coupling, we need to collide hadrons in such way that the cluster of total variations will grow accordingly. That implies we need to collide many hadrons rather than just a few. Since each hadron has energy, as it has mass, that is synonymous with high energy collision. Then once the cluster has been created, there exist an unknown probability of emission of an electron, i.e. the destabilizer. According to the right multiplier of the $2N_k$, which belongs to the prime, the Boson than will appear. At high energies, suppose one of those Bosons was detected. It is immediately creating an option for a creation of an higher magnitude Boson. As an example:

$$\gamma + \gamma + W^- = 13$$

$$13 \in \mathbb{P}$$

That Boson is associated with the sixth coupling term:

$$(120,120 + (3)) + 13 = 120,136$$

Assuming that Boson has a lifetime that is unknown but still present approximately stable behavior, using two Bosons of the weak interaction we can reach again to an higher Boson:

$$13 + \gamma + \gamma = 23$$

So the paper present two major ways in which those Bosons can be detected. First by colliding hadron formations to reach bigger formations. That lepton propagation and from there net variation from the Lepton. The second, once Bosons are at the same space they can morph into higher coupling Bosons in odd combinations, given by the primorial. Those new coupling Bosons are in somewhat of a Superposition of Bosons, they composed by combinations of distinct Bosons. That means that it is possible to detect them based on set of possible decays. As to test, the 8T author will provide a set of possible decays, which can be used to examine the 8T primorial, each Prime is isomorphic to a Boson:

$$W^- + W^- + \gamma = 11$$

$$W^- + W^- + g = 7$$

$$W^- + g + g = \gamma$$

$$W^- + W^- + W^- + g + g = 11$$

$$\gamma + \gamma + W^- = 13$$

$$13 + 7 + 3 = 23$$

$$23 + 13 + W^- = 49$$

$$49 + W^- + \gamma = 57$$

And on we go endlessly, since there exist an equivalence relation between the electron and the Boson of the second interaction, it is possible to replace them without changing the result. That equivalence relation was at the heart of SUSY variation of the 8T, which based upon aligning the net variations on the same term of N_V .

$$W^- \equiv (e) \tag{1.61}$$

The morphisms ignore the fact that the gluon is "confined" within the hadron. However as one can see, the morphisms can occur without the gluon as a direct participator, we can regard the $N_V = +7$ to be an independent element and not nested by lower magnitude primes (and one). Summing up, the larger the energy the higher the chance to observe those weaker coupling terms, the high energy collisions also creating a setting in which those higher coupling terms can morph into even higher coupling terms. Alone those terms are stronger, but as they are part of a much bigger cluster they get weaker from term to term. The strongest term has the smallest cluster, as previously mentioned in the 8T, as dictated by the arrow of time.

$$\begin{array}{c} 0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \\ \hline \frac{1}{9} > \frac{3}{30} > \frac{5}{128} > \frac{7}{850} \dots \end{array}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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